

Mast Cells in Breast Cancer: A Correlation with SBR Grade, Hormone Receptor and Lymphnode Status

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Abstract:

Introduction: Breast carcinoma is the most common non-skin malignancy among women. It is a complex disease in terms of microscopic features, therapeutic response, metastasis and patient outcome. The tumor associated mast cells are response to chemotactic factors released by tumour or its micro-environment. They contain molecules which promote survival with neovascularisation and matrix metalloproteases, needed for tumor invasion and metastasis.

Objectives: To study the correlation of mean mast cell per high power field with Scarff Bloom Richardson grading, hormone receptor status and lymphnode status.

Methods: Eighty surgically resected cases of breast carcinoma were included in the study. H&E stained and IHC Slides were retrieved from departmental archives. Metachromatic stain using 0.1% Toluidine Blue was done on tumour tissue. Mast cells were counted using high power objective. Mean average of 10 HPF were derived and correlated with SBR grade, hormone receptor status and lymph node status.

Results: In the study IDC NOS was most common histopathological type. Mean age of patients was 52.1 years with female predominance. Tumors belonging to SBR grade 1, ER positive tumours had higher mean mast cell count. However, mean mast cell count decreased with increased number of lymph nodes infiltrated by tumour cells.

Conclusion: Mast cell count showed higher numbers with lower SBR grade of tumour and high numbers were noted with ER positive, PR positive and Her 2 neu positive tumours. However, mean mast cell count were less as the number of lymph nodes showing metastatic deposits increased.

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Introduction

Breast carcinoma is the most prevalent tumour among women with an age adjusted rate of 25.8 per 100000 women and mortality of 12.7 per 100000 women [1]. Breast cancer is a complex disease in terms of microscopic features, therapeutic response, metastasis, and patient's outcomes [2]. Due to an increase in modalities to detect the breast carcinomas early, along with treatment with specific adjuvant therapy, the morbidity and mortality rates have reduced in the recent times. An interest to study the prognostic factors has increased [3]. The tumour cells cause expression of certain antigens causing an immune response in stroma [4]. Cancer research till date is mainly focused on malignant cells, while non-malignant components are less investigated. Factors that influence the tumor microenvironment, behavior, metastatic propensity and the course of disease are now being better understood. This makes the tumor microenvironment an interesting subject for study [5]. Tumor associated mast cells (TAMC)

are one of the inflammatory cells which are found in the malignant stroma [1]. Role of mast cells in tissue remodelling events and effective immune responses to infection have been noticed in solid tumors, such as thyroid, gastric, pancreas, bladder cancers and Merkel cell carcinoma, almost always appearing to be pro-tumorigenic [6]. In breast cancer, mast cells almost always appear to play an antitumorigenic role [7].

Materials and Methods

This was a retrospective cross-sectional study, conducted after obtaining necessary clearance from institutional ethics committee, for a period of 24 months. Eighty surgically resected cases of breast carcinoma were included in the study. Cases where chemotherapy was received prior to surgical resection, needle core biopsies were eliminated from the study. The Haematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) stained slides along with Immunohistochemistry

(IHC) slides of the cases were retrieved from the departmental archives and reviewed by two pathologists. Grading of the tumour was done according to Scarff-Bloom - Richardson (SBR) grading. The IHC slides were scored according to Allred scoring system for Estrogen Receptor and Progesterone Receptor and Her2neu interpretation was done according to the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) guidelines. For, metachromatic staining for mast cells, a single section was selected by consensus that had tumor with adjacent stroma showing dense inflammatory infiltrate and stained using 0.1% Toluidine blue. The mast cells were identified by purplish granules in the cytoplasm (Figure 1) and counted using Labomed LX 400 microscope which has a field diameter of 0.67mm. Mean mast cell count from 10hpf was considered and correlated with hormone receptor status, SBR grade and lymph node status of the tumor. Data entry was done in Microsoft Excel and analyzed by SPSS software (v 20). Continuous and categorical were expressed in mean (SD) and count (%) respectively. Independent-t-test was used compare the continuous variable across two groups. Pearson's correlation was used for finding the correlation. p value <0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results

The study included 80 surgically resected cases of carcinoma breast. Mean age of the patients was noted to be 52.1 years with an age range of 32 - 72 years. Most of the cases were found in age group of 41-50 years.

Female predominance was noted with M:F being 1:39. Most common microscopic type noted was infiltrating ductal carcinoma - not otherwise specified with 74 cases (92.5%), followed by invasive lobular carcinoma with 03 cases (3.75%), mucinous carcinoma with 02 cases (2.5%) and a

single case of infiltrating ductal carcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation (1.25%). The cases were graded according to modified SBR grading. 20 cases (26%) belonged to grade 1, 49 cases (64%) belonged to grade 2, 08 cases (10%) belonged to grade 3 (Figure 2). A mean mast cell count/hpf of 13.01 +/- 04.25, 8.87 +/- 3.33 and 3.74 +/- 0.74 was noted in cases belonging to modified SBR grade 1, 2 and 3 respectively. These values were statistically significant with p value <0.01 according to independent t test. Mast cells were noticed to be present in higher numbers in Grade 1 tumors followed by Grade 2 tumors and the least numbers in Grade 3 tumors. On immunohistochemistry, ER was positive in 41 (51.25%) tumors and negative in 39 (48.75%) of tumors. PR was positive in 34 (42.5%) tumors and negative in 46 (57.5%) of tumors. Her 2 neu was negative in 66 (82.5%) tumors, weakly positive in 03 (03.75%) tumors and strongly positive in 11(13.75%) tumors (Figure 2).

The mean mast cell count was noted to be higher in ER positive tumors (11.29 +/- 04.14) than in ER negative tumors (07.84 +/- 04.05). The p-value was noted to be significant for ER positive being <0.01 according to Independent t test. The mean mast cell count was noted to be higher in PR positive tumors (11.29 +/- 04.14) than in PR negative tumors (07.84 +/- 04.05). The p-value was noted to be significant for PR positive being <0.01 according to Independent t test. The mean mast cell count was noted to be higher in Her 2 neu weakly positive tumors (12.17 +/- 03.61), than in strongly positive tumors (11.45 +/- 06.35) and in negative tumors (09.13 +/- 04). The p-value was not significant for Her 2 neu positivity being 0.161 according to Independent t test. There was no correlation between mean mast cells/hpf and lymph node involvement (%) with at correlation coefficient of p=0.06 which was statistically not significant at p > 0.05. (Table 1)

Figure 1: Intratumoral mast cells stained with toluidine blue, 40x, Inset: Mast cell, 100x

Figure 2: Fig 2. a. Infiltrating ductal carcinoma SBR grade 1, 10x, b. Infiltrating ductal carcinoma SBR grade 2, 10x, c. Infiltrating ductal carcinoma SBR grade 3, 10x, d. IHC showing Estrogen Receptor positivity, 40x, e. IHC showing Progesterone Receptor positivity, 40x, f. IHC showing HER2 neu positivity, 40x.

Table 1: Mean mast cell count in relation to SBR grade, Hormone receptor status and lymphnode status

Parameter	Total cases	Percentage	Average no. of mast cells	p value
Scarff- Bloom Richardson Grading				
Grade 1	20	26	13.01 +/- 04.25	< 0.0001
Grade 2	49	64	8.87 +/- 3.33	
Grade 3	8	10	3.74 +/- 0.74	
Hormone Receptor Status				
Estrogen Receptor				
Negative	39	48.75	7.84 +/- 4.05	< 0.0001
Positive	41	51.25	11.29 +/- 4.14	
Progesterone Receptor				
Negative	46	57.5	7.84 +/- 4.05	< 0.0001
Positive	34	42.5	11.29 +/- 4.14	
Her 2 Neu				
Negative (0,1+)	66	82.5	9.13 +/- 4.0	>0.05
Weakly Positive (2+)	3	3.75	12.17+/-3.61	
Strongly Positive (3+)	11	13.75	11.45 +/- 6.35	
Lymphnode Status				
pN0	40	50	9.61=-/4.56	>0.05
pN1	21	26.25	10.90=-/4.41	
pN2	9	11.25	8.23+/-3.85	
pN3	10	12.5	8.47+/-4.10	

Discussion:

The tumour microenvironment is a response against the tumor cells by the host immunity. The micro environment contains fibroblast, endothelial cells, inflammatory cells and extra cellular matrix [4]. It is responsible for tumour development, neo-angiogenesis, metastatic propensity of the tumour

and also the defense against the tumour, thus affecting the outcome of the patient [7]. Virchow showed a link between cancer and inflammation in the 19th century in his hypothesis [1].

Paul Ehrlich in 1878, initially reported the presence of mast cells in human cancers. Since then, such cells are termed as tumour associated mast cells

(TAMC). Mast cells are common in the peritumoral stroma, with a tendency to surround the tumor nest, and release biologically active substances that affect various targets. In majority of the studies, TAMCs appear functional, either actively promoting or suppressing tumor development while in a few cases they are inert bystanders [6,7]. The granules in mast cells particularly stain with a metachromatic dye - toluidine blue. It is the cationic dye with properties tending to polymerise with basic dyes giving a purplish colour to granules. Microscopically, mast cells are mononuclear round to oval cells having granular cytoplasm. The granules contain heparin like molecules, histamine and growth factors such as vascular endothelial growth factors (VEGF-A, - B, - C, - D) platelet derived growth factor, stem cell factor, nerve growth factor which promote the survival of tumor with neo-vascularisation. They contain matrix metalloproteases (MMP9) needed for tumor invasion and metastasis. The mast cells secrete cytokines (CXCL1, CXCL10, and CXCL12), interleukins, proteases (tryptase and chymase), peroxides which induce apoptosis in the tumor cells and digestion of extra cellular membrane favoring the implantation of cancer cells in an aberrant microenvironment [7,8]. Treatments that enhance local mast cell degranulation may induce a variety of antitumor immune mechanisms including the enhanced recruitment of effector cells, the direct impact of granule-associated and de novo synthesized mediators on tumor cells and secondary impacts on immune regulation. Pyla RD et al [9] studied a total of 75 cases, of which majority of the cases (27) belonged to Grade 2 with mean mast cell count 18.44±18.33. Divyarani MN et al [10] studied total of 55 cases of which, majority of the cases (38) belonged to Grade 2 with mean count of 2.82±2.24, which were similar to our study. However, Glajcar A et al [8] studied total of 108 cases of which majority of the cases (54) belonged to grade 3 with mean mast cell count of 18.87±10.22. All these studies showed the grade of tumor and mean mast cell count are inversely related with lower mast cell count in higher grade tumors. Fakhrijou A et al [3] studied 25 cases in each grade. They found mast cell count and SBR grade were

directly proportional as the grade of the tumor increased mast cell count also increased (Table 2). Pyla RD et al [9], Glajcar A et al [8], and the present study had similar findings that ER positive, PR positive and Her2neu positive tumors had increased mast cell count than ER negative, PR negative and Her 2 neu negative tumors (Table 3). In the present study, we observed mast cells count reduced as the staging of the lymphnode increased, in node positive tumors. However, node negative tumors had mast cell count almost similar to PN1 stage tumors. Mast cells have a slow rate of cell division, which will likely also make them more resistant to several common classes of chemotherapeutic drugs than rapidly dividing immune cells. An alternate strategy that may hold promise in the effective induction of anti-tumor immunity and avoid potential systemic side effects of degranulating mast cell activation is the use of therapeutic strategies that selectively activate the primary role of mast cells.

Conclusion

The host defence against the tumor cells can cause an outpour of cytokines in the tumor micro-environment. This leads to infiltration of the tumoral and the peritumoral stroma by inflammatory cells. One amongst them is the mast cell.

We conclude in our study, the mean mast cell count was inversely proportional to the grade of the tumor, proportional to hormone receptor positivity. As the number of lymphnode showing metastatic deposits increase, mean mast cell count is seen to decrease and can act as surrogate marker in prognostication. Mast cells act as antitumoral agent in the prognostic implication of SBR grade, hormone receptor status and lymphnode metastasis in cases of breast carcinoma. With limited studies on mast cells in cases of carcinoma breast, further studies involving larger population with follow up of the patients can help to define their exact role.

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Table 2: Comparison of mean mast cell count among different SBR grades in different studies.

Study	Total no of cases	Grade 1		Grade 2		Grade 3	
		Cases	Mean Mast cell count	Cases	Mean Mast cell count	Cases	Mean Mast cell count
Divyarani MN et al. [10]	55	11	3.27±2.00	38	2.82±2.24	06	2.82±2.12
Pyla RD et al [9]	75	20	24.05±13.92	27	18.44±18.33	13	07.92±6.15
Fakhrijou A et al. [3]	75	25	15.92±10.17	25	45.32±10.47	25	67.80±20.70
Glajcar A et al. [8]	108	17	24.41±10.24	37	23.46±11.81	54	15.87±10.22
Present study	80	20	13.01±4.25	49	8.87 ± 3.33	8	3.74 ± 0.74

Table 3: Comparison of mean mast cell count among hormone receptor status in different studies.

Study	Total cases	ER positive		PR positive		HER 2 NEU positive	
		No of cases	Mean mast cell count	No of cases	mean mast cell count	No of cases	Mean mast cell count
Pyla RD et al. [9]	75	36	23.55±17.02	33	24.18±18.09	28	20.82±17.99
Glajcar A et al [8]	108	30	22.59±10.38	19	27.72±12.76	30	15.30±7.89
Present study	80	41	11.29+/-4.14	34	11.69+/-4.36	11	11.45 ± 6.39

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